

1 **Genes important for chronic viral infection in HBV.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We defined here by measurement of total transcription following RNA-sequencing the set of genes
7 required for chronic viral infection in humans with Hepatitis B infection. We describe activation of the DNA
8 polymerase *Poli* in chronic HBV infection.

9 Citations

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